

Reducing Acceptance Marks in Emerson-Lei Automata by QBF Solving

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel application of QBF solving to automata reduction. We focus on *Transition-based Emerson-Lei automata (TELA)*, which is a popular formalism that generalizes many traditional kinds of automata over infinite words including Büchi, co-Büchi, Rabin, Streett, and parity automata. Transitions in a TELA are labelled with acceptance marks and its accepting formula is a positive Boolean combination of atoms saying that a particular mark has to be visited infinitely or finitely often. Algorithms processing these automata are often very sensitive to the number of acceptance marks. We introduce a new technique for reducing the number of acceptance marks in TELA based on satisfiability of *quantified Boolean formulas (QBF)*. We evaluated our reduction technique on TELA produced by state-of-the-art tools of the libraries Owl and Spot and by the tool `lt13tela`. The technique reduced some acceptance marks in automata produced by all the tools. On automata with more than one acceptance mark obtained by translation of LTL formulas from literature with tools Delag and Rabinizer 4, our technique reduced 27.7% and 39.3% of acceptance marks, respectively. The reduction was even higher on automata from random formulas.

2012 ACM Subject Classification Theory of computation → Logic; Theory of computation → Automata over infinite objects

Keywords and phrases Emerson-Lei automata, TELA, automata reduction, QBF, `telatko`

Digital Object Identifier 10.4230/LIPIcs.SAT.2023.23

Supplementary Material *Software*: <https://gitlab.fi.muni.cz/xschar3/telatko>
archived at `swh:1:dir:ce6c69759d7317f0bc9cb2dc2cc96e9473ca31cd`

Funding T. Schwarzová received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe program under the Grant Agreement No. 101087529.

1 Introduction

Automata over infinite words like Büchi, Rabin, Streett, or parity automata play a crucial role in many algorithms related to concurrency theory, game theory, and formal methods in general. In particular, they are used in specification, verification, analysis, monitoring, and synthesis of various systems with infinite behaviour. In 1987, Emerson and Lei [12] introduced automata over infinite words where acceptance conditions are arbitrary combinations of acceptance primitives saying that a certain set of states should be visited finitely often or infinitely often. In 2015, the same kind of acceptance condition was described in the *Hanoi omega-automata format (HOAF)* [3]. The only difference is that the acceptance primitives talk about finitely or infinitely often visited acceptance marks rather than sets of states. Acceptance marks are placed on transitions and each mark identifies the set of transitions containing this mark. Hence, these automata are called *transition-based Emerson-Lei automata (TELA)* and they generalize many traditional kinds of automata over infinite words including Büchi, co-Büchi, Rabin, Streett, and parity automata.

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26th International Conference on Theory and Applications of Satisfiability Testing (SAT 2023).

Editors: Meena Mahajan and Friedrich Slivovsky; Article No. 23; pp. 23:1–23:20

Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics

LIPICs Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik, Dagstuhl Publishing, Germany

TELA have attracted a lot of attention during the last few years [5, 15, 16, 18]. Their popularity comes probably from the fact that these automata can often use fewer states than equivalent automata with simpler acceptance conditions. Further, algorithms handling TELA can automatically handle all automata with traditional acceptance conditions. TELA can be obtained for example by translating formulas of *linear temporal logic (LTL)* [17] with tools `lt12dela` (known as Delag) [16] or `lt12dgra` (known as Rabinizer 4) [13] of the Owl library, `lt12tgba` of the Spot library [9], or `lt13tela` [15]. There are also algorithms processing these automata, for example the emptiness check [5] or translation of TELA to parity automata [18, 7].

Algorithms processing TELA are often sensitive to the number of acceptance marks more than to other parts of the automaton. For example, the transformation of TELA to parity automata based on *color appearance record* [18] transforms a TELA with m acceptance marks and s states into a parity automaton with up to $m! \cdot s$ states. Further, the emptiness-check algorithm [5] is exponential in the number of acceptance marks that appear in acceptance primitives saying that a mark has to be visited finitely often, while it is only polynomial in other measures of the input automaton.

The number of acceptance marks can be algorithmically reduced to one as every TELA can be transformed to an equivalent Büchi automaton (this can be easily done for example by Spot [9]), but this reduction is paid by dramatic changes of state space: the number of states can increase exponentially in the number of acceptance marks and some important structural properties like determinism can be lost. This motivates our study of a technique reducing the number of acceptance marks without altering the structure of the automaton.

Our reduction technique is heavily based on *quantified Boolean formulas (QBF)*. For a given TELA and parameters C, K , it produces a QBF which is satisfiable if and only if there exists an automaton with the same structure, K acceptance marks, an acceptance formula in disjunctive normal form with C cubes (i.e., conjunction of literals), and the same set of accepting runs as the original automaton. The placement of the marks on transitions and the acceptance formula can be obtained from a model of the formula. Besides this formula, we describe also the construction of two simpler formulas whose satisfiability implies the existence of an automaton with the same structure, K acceptance marks, and the same set of accepting runs, but not vice versa.

We have implemented our reduction technique in a tool called `telatko`. We show that the tool can reduce acceptance marks in automata produced by Delag [16], Rabinizer 4 [13] (both included in the Owl library), Spot [9], and `lt13tela` [15]. While the reduction is relatively modest on TELA produced by `lt13tela` and Spot, it is substantial on automata produced by the tools of the Owl library.

Related results

There is a simple technique [4] reducing the number of acceptance marks in *transition-based generalised Büchi automata (TGBA)* without changing its structure. We are not aware of any existing research aimed at simplification of acceptance formulas of TELA or reduction of the number of its acceptance marks without increasing the number of states. There exists only a SAT-based approach that transforms a deterministic TELA to an equivalent automaton with a given acceptance condition and a given number of states [2] (if such an automaton exists). Further, there are some SAT-based approaches aimed to reduce the number of states of automata over infinite words. More precisely, there are reductions designed for nondeterministic Büchi automata [11], deterministic Büchi automata [10], and deterministic

generalized Büchi automata [1]. Note that these techniques are usually very slow and their authors typically suggest to use them only for specific purposes like looking for cases where some automata construction can be improved.

Casares, Colcombet, and Fijalkow very recently introduced a structure called *alternating cycle decomposition (ACD)* [6] which compactly represents all accepting and non-accepting automata cycles. We expect that ACD could be used to reduce the number of acceptance marks or to simplify the acceptance condition. However, such a reduction is not obvious.

Structure of the paper

The next section introduces basic terms used in the paper. Section 3 explains the construction of the three mentioned quantified Boolean formulas. The reduction algorithm based on these formulas is presented in Section 4. Section 5 describes our tool `telatko` implementing the reduction technique. Experimental results are shown in Section 6. Finally, Section 7 suggests other applications of our QBF-based reduction technique and closes the paper.

2 Preliminaries

In this section we recall the basic terms related to TELA and QBF.

► **Definition 1 (TELA).** A transition-based Emerson-Lei automaton (TELA) is a tuple $\mathcal{A} = (Q, M, \Sigma, \delta, q_I, \varphi)$, where

- Q is a finite set of states,
- M is a finite set of acceptance marks,
- Σ is a finite alphabet,
- $\delta \subseteq Q \times \Sigma \times 2^M \times Q$ is a transition relation,
- $q_I \in Q$ is an initial state, and
- φ is the acceptance condition constructed according to the following abstract syntax equation, where m ranges over M .

$$\varphi ::= \text{true} \mid \text{false} \mid \text{Inf } m \mid \text{Fin } m \mid (\varphi \wedge \varphi) \mid (\varphi \vee \varphi)$$

A tuple $t = (p, a, M', q) \in \delta$ is the *transition* leading from state p to state q labelled with a and acceptance marks M' . The set M' is also referred to by $\text{mks}(t)$. For a set of transitions $T \subseteq \delta$, let $\text{mks}(T) = \bigcup_{t \in T} \text{mks}(t)$ denote the set of marks that appear on transitions in T .

A *run* π of \mathcal{A} over an infinite word $u = u_0u_1u_2\dots \in \Sigma^\omega$ is an infinite sequence of adjacent transitions $\pi = (q_0, u_0, M_0, q_1)(q_1, u_1, M_1, q_2)\dots \in \delta^\omega$ where $q_0 = q_I$. Let $\text{inf}(\pi)$ denote the set of transitions that appear infinitely many times in π . Run π is *accepting* iff $\text{inf}(\pi)$ satisfies the formula φ , where a set T of transitions satisfies $\text{Inf } m$ iff $m \in \text{mks}(T)$ and it satisfies $\text{Fin } m$ iff $m \notin \text{mks}(T)$. The *language* of \mathcal{A} is the set $L(\mathcal{A}) = \{u \in \Sigma^\omega \mid \text{there is an accepting run of } \mathcal{A} \text{ over } u\}$. Two automata \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} are *equivalent* if $L(\mathcal{A}) = L(\mathcal{B})$.

An acceptance formula φ is in *disjunctive normal form (DNF)* if it is a disjunction of cubes, where each cube is a conjunction of atoms of the form $\text{Fin } m$ or $\text{Inf } m$. Each acceptance formula can be transformed into an equivalent formula in DNF. Formula *false* corresponds to the disjunction of zero cubes and formula *true* corresponds to the cube with zero atoms.

A *path* from a state p to a state q is a finite sequence of adjacent transitions of the form $\rho = (q_0, u_0, M_0, q_1)(q_1, u_1, M_1, q_2)\dots(q_{n-1}, u_{n-1}, M_{n-1}, q_n) \in \delta^+$ such that $p = q_0$ and $q = q_n$. A nonempty set of states $S \subseteq Q$ is called a nontrivial *strongly connected component (SCC)* if for each $p, q \in S$ there is a path from p to q . An SCC S is *maximal* if there is no SCC S' satisfying $S \subsetneq S'$. In the rest of this paper, SCC always refers to a maximal SCC.

Given a set of states $S \subseteq Q$, let $\delta_S = \delta \cap (S \times \Sigma \times 2^M \times S)$ denote the set of all transitions between states in S . Further, for each mark $m \in M$, let $\delta_m = \{t \in \delta \mid m \in mks(t)\}$ denote the set of all transitions marked with m . A set of transitions $T \subseteq \delta$ is called a *cycle* if there exists a path from a state p to the same state containing each transition of T at least once and no transition outside T . Finally, we assume that each TELA \mathcal{A} contains only states q that are reachable from the initial state q_I (i.e., $q = q_I$ or there is a path from q_I to q) as states that are not reachable from q_I can be eliminated without any impact on $L(\mathcal{A})$. We also assume that each TELA has at least one SCC as automata without any SCC trivially describe an empty language.

In graphical representation, we often use acceptance marks $\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}, \dots \in M$. Further, an edge $(p) \xrightarrow{a} (q)$ denotes the transition $(p, a, \{\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{k}\}, q) \in \delta$.

By choosing an appropriate acceptance condition, one can easily represent many classical kinds of automata over infinite words. For example, a Büchi automaton can be represented as a TELA with the acceptance condition $\varphi = \text{Inf } \mathbf{1}$ and the single mark $\mathbf{1}$ placed on all transitions leaving the accepting states of the Büchi automaton. Further, a Rabin automaton with k acceptance pairs can be similarly represented as a TELA with acceptance condition $\varphi = (\text{Fin } \mathbf{1} \wedge \text{Inf } \mathbf{1}') \vee \dots \vee (\text{Fin } \mathbf{k} \wedge \text{Inf } \mathbf{k}')$ and marks $M = \{\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{1}', \dots, \mathbf{k}, \mathbf{k}'\}$.

Quantified Boolean formulas (QBF) are Boolean formulas extended with universal and existential quantification over propositional variables. We assume that subformulas of the form $\forall x.\psi$ and $\exists x.\psi$ do not contain another quantification of variable x inside ψ . The semantics of $\forall x.\psi$ and $\exists x.\psi$ is given by equivalences

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x.\psi &\equiv \psi[x \rightarrow \text{true}] \wedge \psi[x \rightarrow \text{false}] \\ \exists x.\psi &\equiv \psi[x \rightarrow \text{true}] \vee \psi[x \rightarrow \text{false}] \end{aligned}$$

where $\psi[x \rightarrow \rho]$ denotes the formula ψ with all occurrences of x simultaneously replaced by ρ . The equivalences imply that each QBF can be transformed into an equivalent Boolean formula. However, the size of this Boolean formula can be exponential in the size of the original QBF. Let V be the set of all propositional variables. A mapping $\mu : V \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a *model* of a QBF φ iff it is a satisfying assignment of an equivalent Boolean formula. A QBF is *satisfiable* iff it has a model.

3 Construction of quantified Boolean formulas

Recall that we aim to reduce the number of acceptance marks in a given TELA $\mathcal{A} = (Q, M, \Sigma, \delta, q_I, \varphi)$ without altering its structure and language. In other words, we look for

- a set N of acceptance marks satisfying $|N| < |M|$,
- an acceptance formula ψ over N , and
- a function $nm : \delta \rightarrow Q \times \Sigma \times 2^N \times Q$ assigning new marks to transitions (i.e., for each $t = (p, a, M', q) \in \delta$, we assume that $nm(t) = (p, a, N', q)$ for some $N' \subseteq N$) such that the automaton $\mathcal{B} = (Q, N, \Sigma, nm(\delta), q_I, \psi)$ is equivalent to \mathcal{A} .

We will actually look for ψ and nm such that each run $\pi = t_0 t_1 t_2 \dots$ of \mathcal{A} is accepting if and only if the run $nm(t_0) nm(t_1) nm(t_2) \dots$ of \mathcal{B} is accepting. This requirement clearly guarantees the equivalence of \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , but it is not a necessary condition for the equivalence. Indeed, there exist automata where relaxing this requirement can lead to a bigger reduction of acceptance marks (see Figure 1). However, looking for ψ and nm that preserve the acceptance of individual runs makes the problem easier as we can, for example, ignore the labelling of transitions by the elements of Σ .

■ **Figure 1** The left automaton accepts the words that contain infinitely many occurrences of both a and b . Each accepting run of the left automaton has to contain infinitely many occurrences of both transitions looping on the initial state. Hence, there does not exist any automaton with the same accepting runs as the left automaton and less than two acceptance marks. The right automaton accepts the same language using one acceptance mark and a different set of accepting runs.

Our reduction method is based on two facts. First, the acceptance of a run π is fully determined by $\text{inf}(\pi)$. Second, each set $\text{inf}(\pi)$ is a cycle and vice versa.

► **Lemma 2.** *A set $T \subseteq \delta$ is a cycle if and only if there is a run π such that $\text{inf}(\pi) = T$.*

Proof. To prove the direction “ \implies ”, we assume that T is a cycle. The definition says that there exists a path τ from a state p to the same state containing each transition of T at least once and no transition outside T . As our automata contain only reachable states, there exists a path ρ from the initial state q_I to p or $p = q_I$ and we set $\rho = \varepsilon$. The infinite sequence $\pi = \rho.\tau^\omega$ is a run satisfying $\text{inf}(\pi) = T$.

To prove the direction “ \impliedby ”, we consider a run π . As $\text{inf}(\pi)$ is the set of transitions that appear infinitely many times in π , there has to be a suffix π' of π containing only transitions of $\text{inf}(\pi)$. Let p be the first state of π' . As each transition of π' appears infinitely many times in π and thus also in π' , there has to be a finite prefix ρ of π' such that ρ is a path from p to p that contains all transitions of $\text{inf}(\pi)$. In other words, the set $\text{inf}(\pi)$ is a cycle. ◀

Hence, our goal can be reformulated as follows. We look for a new acceptance formula ψ and a function nm such that for each cycle $T \subseteq \delta$, it holds that T satisfies φ if and only if $nm(T)$ satisfies ψ . This can be roughly denoted by the formula

$$\forall T \subseteq \delta . \text{cycle}(T) \implies (\text{satisfies}_\varphi(T) \iff \text{satisfies}_\psi(nm(T))).$$

In fact, this corresponds to the shape of the QBF we will construct. As we are looking for ψ and nm such that the formula holds, the subformula $\text{satisfies}_\psi(nm(T))$ contains many free variables representing possible instances of ψ and nm . If the formula is satisfiable, then each of its models encodes a desired instance of ψ and nm . In the following, we assume that we are looking for a new acceptance formula ψ in DNF. The choice of DNF is not fundamental, but inherited from our previous attempt to reduce acceptance formulas. The presented method can be easily adapted to look for ψ in *conjunctive normal form (CNF)* or in a different shape.

Now we describe the construction of the QBF in detail. The construction is parameterized by two integers $C, K \geq 0$, where K is the desired number of acceptance marks and C is the number of cubes of ψ . Without loss of generality, we assume that the reduced automaton will use the acceptance marks $N_K = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$. We start with a description of Boolean variables used in the constructed QBF.

■ For each transition $t \in \delta$, variable e_t says whether t is in the current set T or not.

$$e_t = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t \in T \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

23:6 Reducing Acceptance Marks in Emerson-Lei Automata by QBF Solving

- For each transition $t \in \delta$ and acceptance mark $k \in N_K$, variable $n_{t,k}$ says whether k is on the transition $nm(t)$ or not.

$$n_{t,k} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k \in mks(nm(t)) \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

- For each $c \in \{1, 2, \dots, C\}$ and acceptance mark $k \in N_K$, variables $i_{c,k}$ and $f_{c,k}$ say whether the c^{th} cube of ψ contains atoms $\text{Inf } k$ or $\text{Fin } k$, respectively.

$$i_{c,k} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the } c^{\text{th}} \text{ cube of } \psi \text{ contains } \text{Inf } k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$f_{c,k} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the } c^{\text{th}} \text{ cube of } \psi \text{ contains } \text{Fin } k \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

By $\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f}$ we denote the vectors of all variables of the form $e_t, n_{t,k}, i_{c,k}$, and $f_{c,k}$, respectively. The constructed QBF have the form

$$\Phi_{C,K}(\vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f}) = \forall \vec{e}. \text{cycle}(\vec{e}) \implies (\text{satisfies}_\varphi(\vec{e}) \iff \text{satisfies}_{C,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})),$$

where $\forall \vec{e}$ denotes the sequence composed of $\forall e_t$ for all variables e_t . Now we define the subformulas $\text{satisfies}_\varphi(\vec{e})$, $\text{satisfies}_{C,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})$, and three versions of $\text{cycle}(\vec{e})$.

The subformula $\text{satisfies}_\varphi(\vec{e})$ says whether T satisfies the original acceptance formula φ and it is derived directly from φ . Recall that T satisfies $\text{Inf } m$ iff $m \in mks(T)$, which means that T contains some transition with mark m . As the transitions with mark m form the set δ_m , $\text{Inf } m$ can be expressed by $\bigvee_{t \in \delta_m} e_t$. Similarly, T satisfies $\text{Fin } m$ iff $m \notin mks(T)$, which can be expressed by $\bigwedge_{t \in \delta_m} \neg e_t$. Hence, $\text{satisfies}_\varphi(\vec{e})$ arises from φ by replacing

- all atoms of the form $\text{Inf } m$ by $\bigvee_{t \in \delta_m} e_t$ and
- all atoms of the form $\text{Fin } m$ by $\bigwedge_{t \in \delta_m} \neg e_t$.

Next, we construct the subformula $\text{satisfies}_{C,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})$ that evaluates to true iff $nm(T)$ satisfies ψ . The subformula reflects the basic structure of ψ . As we assume that ψ is a disjunction of C cubes, we have

$$\text{satisfies}_{C,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f}) = \bigvee_{c \in \{1, 2, \dots, C\}} \xi_{c,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})$$

where each $\xi_{c,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})$ corresponds to one cube. Recall that the presence of atoms $\text{Inf } k$ and $\text{Fin } k$ in the c^{th} cube is given by variables $i_{c,k}$ and $f_{c,k}$, respectively. $\text{Inf } k$ is satisfied by $nm(T)$ iff T contains a transition t such that $k \in mks(nm(t))$, which can be expressed as $\bigvee_{t \in \delta} (e_t \wedge n_{t,k})$. Similarly, $\text{Fin } k$ is satisfied by $nm(T)$ iff there is no transition $t \in T$ such that $k \in mks(nm(t))$, which can be expressed as $\bigwedge_{t \in \delta} \neg(e_t \wedge n_{t,k})$. Hence, we set

$$\xi_{c,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f}) = \bigwedge_{k \in N_K} \left(i_{c,k} \implies \bigvee_{t \in \delta} (e_t \wedge n_{t,k}) \right) \wedge \left(f_{c,k} \implies \bigwedge_{t \in \delta} \neg(e_t \wedge n_{t,k}) \right).$$

It remains to define the subformula $\text{cycle}(\vec{e})$. Let $T_{\vec{e}}$ denote the set of transitions represented by \vec{e} . The original intended meaning of $\text{cycle}(\vec{e})$ is

$$\text{cycle}(\vec{e}) \iff T_{\vec{e}} \text{ is a cycle.}$$

In fact, only the direction “ \iff ” is needed for the correctness of our reduction method. If there are some valuations of \vec{e} such that $\text{cycle}(\vec{e})$ holds and $T_{\vec{e}}$ is not a cycle, then we

will superfluously require the equivalence $\text{satisfies}_\varphi(\vec{e}) \iff \text{satisfies}_{C,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})$ on these valuations. These superfluous constraints can lead to loss of reduction opportunities, but not to incorrectness. This observation allows us to trade the precision of $\text{cycle}(\vec{e})$ for its simplicity.

We define three versions of $\text{cycle}(\vec{e})$:

- $\text{cycle}_1(\vec{e})$ is a lightweight version, which only says that $T_{\vec{e}}$ is nonempty and $T_{\vec{e}} \subseteq \delta_S$ for some SCC S . Except for SCCs, it does not use the information about the automaton structure, but it comes with an interesting simplification of the whole formula $\Phi_{C,K}$.
- $\text{cycle}_2(\vec{e})$ is an intermediate version. It says that $T_{\vec{e}}$ is nonempty, $T_{\vec{e}} \subseteq \delta_S$ for some SCC S , and every transition in $T_{\vec{e}}$ has a preceding and a succeeding transition in $T_{\vec{e}}$, which is a necessary condition for being a cycle, but not a sufficient one.
- $\text{cycle}_3(\vec{e})$ is a strict version saying that $T_{\vec{e}}$ is a cycle. Unfortunately, it uses additional universally quantified variables corresponding to automata states. Transformation of $\Phi_{C,K}$ to prenex normal form turns the quantifiers to existential ones and the resulting formula thus contains quantifier alternation.

We write $\Phi_{j,C,K}$ when we want to emphasize that a particular formula $\Phi_{C,K}$ contains the version $\text{cycle}_j(\vec{e})$.

3.1 Lightweight version $\text{cycle}_1(\vec{e})$

The lightweight version is defined as

$$\text{cycle}_1(\vec{e}) = \bigvee_{\text{SCC } S} \left(\bigvee_{t \in \delta_S} e_t \wedge \bigwedge_{t' \in \delta \setminus \delta_S} \neg e_{t'} \right)$$

which means only that $T_{\vec{e}}$ is nonempty and $T_{\vec{e}} \subseteq \delta_S$ for some SCC S . This condition is satisfied by every cycle.

The formula $\Phi_{1,C,K}$ built with $\text{cycle}_1(\vec{e})$ says that for every nonempty set $T \subseteq \delta_S$ where S is an SCC, T satisfies φ if and only if $nm(T)$ satisfies ψ . Note that the only aspects of a transition t reflected by the formula are its set of marks $mks(t)$ and its affiliation to an SCC. Hence, we do not have to distinguish between transitions that are affiliated to the same SCC and have the same sets of marks.

Let us now fix an SCC S . We define an equivalence $\sim_S \subseteq \delta_S \times \delta_S$ on transitions such that $t_1 \sim_S t_2$ whenever $mks(t_1) = mks(t_2)$.

► **Lemma 3.** *Assume that there is a function nm and a formula ψ such that*

$$\text{for every set } \emptyset \neq T \subseteq \delta_S \text{ it holds } (T \text{ satisfies } \varphi \iff nm(T) \text{ satisfies } \psi). \quad (1)$$

Then there exists a function nm' that respects the equivalence \sim_S (i.e., it assigns the same marks to equivalent transitions) and

$$\text{for every set } \emptyset \neq T \subseteq \delta_S \text{ it holds } (T \text{ satisfies } \varphi \iff nm'(T) \text{ satisfies } \psi). \quad (2)$$

Proof. Let nm be a function and ψ a formula such that (1) holds. To construct the function nm' , we first select one transition from each equivalence class of \sim_S . For every transition $t = (p, a, M', q) \in \delta_S$, by \bar{t} we denote the selected transition equivalent to t and we define the function nm' such that $nm'(t) = (p, a, mks(nm(\bar{t})), q)$. Note that we do not need to discuss the value of nm' on transitions outside δ_S as it is not relevant for the lemma. Clearly, nm' respects the equivalence \sim_S . It remains to show that (2) holds for nm' and ψ .

■ **Figure 2** An automaton structure (left) and two sets $T_{\vec{e}}$ (middle and right) that are not cycles even if $cycle_2(\vec{e})$ holds. The transition labels and acceptance marks are not depicted.

Let $T \subseteq \delta_S$ be a nonempty set. We construct the set $\bar{T} = \{\bar{t} \mid t \in T\}$. As $mks(t) = mks(\bar{t})$ for all transitions of δ_S , we get $mks(T) = mks(\bar{T})$ and thus

$$T \text{ satisfies } \varphi \iff \bar{T} \text{ satisfies } \varphi.$$

Now we apply (1) to \bar{T} and we get

$$\bar{T} \text{ satisfies } \varphi \iff nm(\bar{T}) \text{ satisfies } \psi.$$

Finally, the definition of nm' implies that $nm'(T) = nm(\bar{T})$ and thus

$$nm(\bar{T}) \text{ satisfies } \psi \iff nm'(T) \text{ satisfies } \psi.$$

Altogether, we obtain

$$T \text{ satisfies } \varphi \iff \bar{T} \text{ satisfies } \varphi \iff nm(\bar{T}) \text{ satisfies } \psi \iff nm'(T) \text{ satisfies } \psi$$

which proves that (2) holds for nm' and ψ . ◀

The lemma suggests the following simplification of the whole formula $\Phi_{1,C,K}$ built with $cycle_1(\vec{e})$. Before we build the formula, we compute the equivalences \sim_S for all SCCs and temporarily remove all transitions affiliated to SCCs except one of each equivalence class. Then we build the formula $\Phi_{1,C,K}$ for the pruned automaton. The more transitions we removed, the shorter formula with less e_t variables we obtain. If the formula $\Phi_{1,C,K}$ for the pruned automaton is satisfiable, we derive nm and ψ from its model and extend nm to all transitions of the original automaton such that it changes the acceptance marks on all equivalent transitions in the same way. In the following, we use this simplification whenever $\Phi_{1,C,K}$ is employed.

3.2 Intermediate version $cycle_2(\vec{e})$

The intermediate version says that $T_{\vec{e}}$ is nonempty, $T_{\vec{e}} \subseteq \delta_S$ for some SCC S , and for each state $q \in Q$ it holds that $T_{\vec{e}}$ contains a transition leading to q if and only if it contains a transition leaving q . Formally,

$$cycle_2(\vec{e}) = cycle_1(\vec{e}) \wedge \bigwedge_{q \in Q} \left(\bigvee_{t' \in \delta \cap Q \times \Sigma \times 2^M \times \{q\}} e_{t'} \iff \bigvee_{t'' \in \delta \cap \{q\} \times \Sigma \times 2^M \times Q} e_{t''} \right).$$

This condition is satisfied by every cycle, but also by some sets of transitions that are not cycles. Some examples of such sets are provided in Figure 2.

3.3 Strict version $cycle_3(\vec{e})$

Before we give the definition of $cycle_3(\vec{e})$, we prove that cycles can be characterised in the following way.

► **Lemma 4.** *A nonempty set $T \subseteq \delta$ is a cycle if and only if, for each set of states $S \subseteq Q$, one of the following conditions holds.*

- A. *All transitions in T lead from a state in S to a state in S (i.e., $T \subseteq \delta_S$).*
- B. *All transitions in T lead from a state outside S to a state outside S (i.e., $T \subseteq \delta_{Q \setminus S}$).*
- C. *T contains a transition leading from a state in S to a state outside S and a transition leading from a state outside S to a state in S .*

Proof. We first prove the direction “ \implies ”. Let T be a cycle and $S \subseteq Q$ be an arbitrary set of states. We show that if (A) and (B) do not hold, then (C) has to hold. Hence, assume that $T \not\subseteq \delta_S$ and $T \not\subseteq \delta_{Q \setminus S}$. Then there are two cases.

- T contains a transition $t \in \delta_S$ and a transition $t' \in \delta_{Q \setminus S}$. The definition of a cycle implies that there exists a path $t_1 t_2 \dots t_n \in T^+$ from a state p back to p containing both t and t' . However, this implies that T contains a transition leading from a state in S to a state outside S and a transition leading from a state outside S to a state in S .
- T contains a transition t leading from a state in S to a state outside S (or vice versa). However, as T is a cycle, there exists a path $t_1 t_2 \dots t_n \in T^+$ that leads from a state p to the same state and contains t . Hence, T has to contain also a transition leading from a state outside S to a state in S (or vice versa).

In both cases, (C) holds.

Now we prove the opposite direction “ \impliedby ” by contraposition. Assume that a nonempty set T is not a cycle. We show that there is a set $S \subseteq Q$ such that neither (A) nor (B) nor (C) holds. Let p be a state such that some transition of T leads from p . We define the set S_{post} of states reachable from p via transitions in T and the set S_{pre} of states from which p is reachable via transitions of T .

$$S_{post} = \{p\} \cup \{q \in Q \mid \text{there is a path in } T^+ \text{ from } p \text{ to } q\}$$

$$S_{pre} = \{p\} \cup \{q \in Q \mid \text{there is a path in } T^+ \text{ from } q \text{ to } p\}$$

As there is a transition of T leading from p , we have that $T \not\subseteq \delta_{Q \setminus S_{post}}$ and $T \not\subseteq \delta_{Q \setminus S_{pre}}$, i.e., (B) does not hold for S_{post} and S_{pre} . Further, the definition of S_{post} implies that there is no transition of T leading from a state in S_{post} to a state outside S_{post} , which means that (C) does not hold for S_{post} . Similarly, T contains no transition leading from a state outside S_{pre} to a state in S_{pre} , which means that (C) does not hold for S_{pre} . Now we prove by contradiction that (A) does not hold for at least one of S_{post}, S_{pre} . Hence, let us assume that $T \subseteq \delta_{S_{post}}$ and $T \subseteq \delta_{S_{pre}}$. Then for each $t_i \in T$ leading from p_i to q_i we have that $p_i \in S_{post}$ and $q_i \in S_{pre}$, which implies that

- $p_i = p$ (we set $\rho'_i = \varepsilon$ in this case) or there is a path $\rho'_i \in T^+$ leading from p to p_i , and
 - $q_i = p$ (we set $\rho''_i = \varepsilon$ in this case) or there is a path $\rho''_i \in T^+$ leading from q_i to p .
- Then there is a path $\rho_i = \rho'_i t_i \rho''_i \in T^+$ leading from p back to p and containing t_i . If we concatenate all these paths, we get the path $\rho_1 \rho_2 \dots \rho_{|T|} \in T^+$ that contains all transitions of T and leads from p back to p , which means that T is a cycle. This is a contradiction. ◀

The formula $cycle_3(\vec{e})$ says that $T_{\vec{e}}$ is nonempty and each set $S \subseteq Q$ satisfies (A) or (B) or (C). For each state $q \in Q$, variable s_q says whether q is in the current set S or not.

$$s_q = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } q \in S \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

23:10 Reducing Acceptance Marks in Emerson-Lei Automata by QBF Solving

By \vec{s} we denote the vectors of all variables of the form s_q . The formula $cycle_3(\vec{e})$ is defined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} cycle_3(\vec{e}) &= \bigvee_{t \in \delta} e_t \wedge \forall \vec{s}. \zeta_A(\vec{e}, \vec{s}) \vee \zeta_B(\vec{e}, \vec{s}) \vee \zeta_C(\vec{e}, \vec{s}) \\ \zeta_A(\vec{e}, \vec{s}) &= \bigwedge_{t=(p,a,M',q) \in \delta} (e_t \implies (s_p \wedge s_q)) \\ \zeta_B(\vec{e}, \vec{s}) &= \bigwedge_{t=(p,a,M',q) \in \delta} (e_t \implies (\neg s_p \wedge \neg s_q)) \\ \zeta_C(\vec{e}, \vec{s}) &= \left(\bigvee_{t=(p,a,M',q) \in \delta} e_t \wedge s_p \wedge \neg s_q \right) \wedge \left(\bigvee_{t=(p,a,M',q) \in \delta} e_t \wedge \neg s_p \wedge s_q \right) \end{aligned}$$

3.4 Complexity of formulas

The constructed formulas $\Phi_{j,C,K}$ for $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ use $|\delta|$ universally quantified variables e_t , $|\delta| \cdot K$ free variables $n_{t,k}$, and $C \cdot K$ free variables $i_{c,k}$ and $f_{c,k}$. The formula $\Phi_{3,C,K}$ additionally uses $|Q|$ variables s_q that are existentially quantified (when the formula is transformed to prenex normal form) in the scope of universal quantification of variables e_t .

To analyze the length of the formulas, we start with its subformulas. One can easily check that $|satisfies_\varphi(\vec{e})| \in \mathcal{O}(|\varphi| \cdot |\delta|)$ and $|satisfies_{C,K}(\vec{e}, \vec{n}, \vec{i}, \vec{f})| \in \mathcal{O}(C \cdot K \cdot |\delta|)$. Further, $|cycle_1(\vec{e})|, |cycle_2(\vec{e})| \in \mathcal{O}(S \cdot |\delta|)$, where S is the number of SCCs in the automaton. Next, $|cycle_3(\vec{e})| \in \mathcal{O}(|\delta| + |Q|)$, which can be simplified to $|cycle_3(\vec{e})| \in \mathcal{O}(|\delta|)$ as $|Q| \leq |\delta|$ follows from the assumptions that all states are reachable and each automaton has at least one SCC. Altogether, we get $|\Phi_{1,C,K}|, |\Phi_{2,C,K}| \in \mathcal{O}(S \cdot |\delta| + |\varphi| \cdot |\delta| + C \cdot K \cdot |\delta|) = \mathcal{O}((S + |\varphi| + C \cdot K) \cdot |\delta|)$ and $|\Phi_{3,C,K}| \in \mathcal{O}(|\delta| + |\varphi| \cdot |\delta| + C \cdot K \cdot |\delta|) = \mathcal{O}((|\varphi| + C \cdot K) \cdot |\delta|)$. Note that the formula $\Phi_{3,C,K}$ is asymptotically shorter than $\Phi_{1,C,K}$ and $\Phi_{2,C,K}$, but it contains an additional quantifier alternation.

3.5 Optimizations of formulas

Finally, we mention three simple optimizations of the formula construction, which are always applied in the rest of the paper.

The first optimization is based on the fact that every cycle is completely included in the transition set δ_S of some SCC S . Hence, all transitions t that do not lead between states of the same SCC can be completely ignored during the formula construction. The acceptance marks on such a transition t do not affect the acceptance of any run as t appears at most once on each run. For these transitions t , we can define $nm(t)$ such that $mks(nm(t)) = \emptyset$.

The second optimization is specific for $\Phi_{3,C,K}$. In the construction of $cycle_3(\vec{e})$, we replace the subformula $\bigvee_{t \in \delta} e_t$ enforcing the nonemptiness of $T_{\vec{e}}$ by $cycle_2(\vec{e})$. This modification prolongs the formula, but it does not change the overall semantics of $cycle_3(\vec{e})$ and our preliminary experiments showed that QBF solvers can often solve the modified formula $\Phi_{3,C,K}$ faster.

The third optimization extends $\Phi_{j,C,K}$ into the conjunction

$$\Phi_{j,C,K} \wedge \bigwedge_{c \in \{1, 2, \dots, C\}} \bigwedge_{k \in N_K} (\neg i_{c,k} \vee \neg f_{c,k}).$$

The added part says that no cube contains both $\text{Inf } k$ and $\text{Fin } k$ for any k . A cube with both $\text{Inf } k$ and $\text{Fin } k$ would be useless as it cannot be satisfied by any run.

■ **Algorithm 1** The single-level reduction procedure.

```

Procedure SingleLevelReduction( $\mathcal{A}, j, reduceC$ )
  Input: TELA  $\mathcal{A} = (Q, M, \Sigma, \delta, q_I, \varphi)$ ,  $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ ,  $reduceC \in \{true, false\}$ 
  Output: an equivalent TELA with the same structure as  $\mathcal{A}$  and with at most as
    many acceptance marks as in  $\mathcal{A}$ 

   $C_{\mathcal{A}} \leftarrow$  the number of cubes in the formula  $\varphi$  transformed to DNF
   $K_{\mathcal{A}} \leftarrow$  the number of acceptance marks in  $\mathcal{A}$ 
   $C \leftarrow C_{\mathcal{A}}$ 
   $K \leftarrow K_{\mathcal{A}}$ 
  while  $K > 1 \wedge satisfiable(\Phi_{j,C,K-1})$  do  $K \leftarrow K-1$ 
  if  $K = 1$  then
    | if all cycles in  $\mathcal{A}$  are accepting then // check the condition true
    | | return  $(Q, \emptyset, \Sigma, \delta', q_I, true)$  where  $\delta'$  is  $\delta$  with all marks removed
    | if all cycles in  $\mathcal{A}$  are rejecting then // check the condition false
    | | return  $(Q, \emptyset, \Sigma, \delta', q_I, false)$  where  $\delta'$  is  $\delta$  with all marks removed
  if  $reduceC$  then // reduction of the number of cubes
  | while  $C > 1 \wedge satisfiable(\Phi_{j,C-1,K})$  do  $C \leftarrow C-1$ 
  if  $K < K_{\mathcal{A}} \vee C < C_{\mathcal{A}}$  then
  | compute  $nm$  and  $\psi$  from a model of  $\Phi_{j,C,K}$ 
  | return  $(Q, N_K, \Sigma, nm(\delta), q_I, \psi)$ 
  return  $\mathcal{A}$ 

```

We have also made some experiments with breaking the symmetries in the formula models. In particular, we have ordered new acceptance marks by their placements on transitions and we have ordered the cubes by their content. As the effect of these modifications was inconclusive, we do not describe it here.

4 Reduction algorithm

This section explains how we use the QBF constructed in the previous section to reduce the number of acceptance marks in TELA. First, we describe a *single-level* reduction, which uses only a single kind of QBF. More precisely, we talk about *level 1*, *level 2*, or *level 3* reduction when $\Phi_{1,C,K}$, $\Phi_{2,C,K}$, or $\Phi_{3,C,K}$ is used, respectively.

The reduction procedure called *SingleLevelReduction* is given in Algorithm 1. Besides the reduction of acceptance marks, the algorithm also reduces the number of cubes in the acceptance formula if the last argument *reduceC* is set to *true*. The first **while** loop gradually decreases the number of marks until $K = 1$ is reached or the QBF solver behind the function *satisfiable*($\Phi_{j,C,K-1}$) fails to reduce the number of marks, i.e., it claims unsatisfiability of the formula or it runs out of resources. If the loop ends with $K = 1$, we check whether an acceptance condition without any mark (i.e., *true* or *false*) can be used. These checks are based on an inspection of the automaton rather than on QBF solving. If some of the checks succeeds, we return the corresponding automaton without any acceptance mark. Otherwise, if *reduceC* is set to *true* then the procedure gradually reduces the number of cubes in the second **while** loop. Note that the loop never checks for acceptance condition with 0 cubes as it is equivalent to *false* and this case was treated above. Finally, if the procedure succeeds to reduce the number of marks or cubes, it constructs the modified automaton. Otherwise, it returns the original automaton.

■ **Figure 3** An example illustrating the results of the three single-level reductions: an input automaton \mathcal{A} and the automata obtained by reducing it with level 1, level 2, and level 3.

The algorithm can be reformulated to use an incremental approach instead of building a new formula in each iteration of the **while** loops. The incremental version of the first **while** loop builds the formula $\Phi = \Phi_{j,C,K-1}$ only in the first iteration. In each subsequent iteration, it extends this formula with a condition saying that one more mark is not used in the automaton, i.e., the mark is neither on edges, nor in the acceptance formula. For example, if we want to say that the mark $k \in N_K$ is not used, we replace Φ by

$$\Phi \wedge \bigwedge_{t \in \delta} \neg n_{t,k} \wedge \bigwedge_{c \in \{1,2,\dots,C\}} (\neg i_{c,k} \wedge \neg f_{c,k}).$$

The second **while** loop can be transformed to an incremental version similarly. The incremental approach benefits from the fact that some QBF solvers can decide an extended formula faster as they reuse the information computed when solving the original formula.

Figure 3 shows a very simple automaton \mathcal{A} and the three automata produced by calls of $SingleLevelReduction(\mathcal{A}, j, true)$ for $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. The figure clearly illustrates that the higher level of reduction we use, the more acceptance marks can be reduced. On the other side, lower levels are typically faster. The best results can be often achieved by combining reductions of all levels. We call this approach *multi-level* reduction. It is a straightforward sequential application of the three levels, see Algorithm 2.

5 Implementation

The presented reduction algorithms have been implemented in a tool called `telatko`. It is implemented in Python 3 and uses the Spot library [9] for automata parsing and manipulation, and the theorem prover Z3 [8] to solve the satisfiability of QBF transformed to prenex (non-CNF) normal form. Our tool is available at

<https://gitlab.fi.muni.cz/xschar3/telatko>

under the GNU GPLv3 license. The tool can be executed by the command

```
telatko -F <input.hoa> [-L j] [-C] [-I] [-T t] [-O <output.hoa>]
```

■ **Algorithm 2** The multi-level reduction procedure.

Procedure *MultiLevelReduction*(\mathcal{A} , *reduceC*)
Input: TELA $\mathcal{A} = (Q, M, \Sigma, \delta, q_I, \varphi)$ and *reduceC* $\in \{true, false\}$
Output: an equivalent TELA with the same structure as \mathcal{A} and with at most as many acceptance marks as in \mathcal{A}

$\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \text{SingleLevelReduction}(\mathcal{A}, 1, false)$
 $\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \text{SingleLevelReduction}(\mathcal{A}, 2, false)$
 $\mathcal{A} \leftarrow \text{SingleLevelReduction}(\mathcal{A}, 3, reduceC)$
return \mathcal{A}

where

- F <input.hoa> specifies the file with the input automaton in HOA format [3],
- L j specifies the reduction level; if omitted, the multi-level reduction is used,
- C switches on the reduction of the number of cubes after the number of marks is reduced (it corresponds to *reduceC* = *true* in Algorithms 1 and 2),
- I switches on the incremental version,
- T t sets the timeout for each QBF query to t seconds (the default value is 50 seconds),
- O <output.hoa> specifies the output file; if omitted, the produced automaton is sent to *stdout* in the HOA format.

If some call of the function *satisfiable*($\Phi_{j,C,K-1}$) in the first **while** loop of Algorithm 1 does not return *true*, then the name of the output automaton (included in the generated HOA) encodes the reason for it. In the case of a single level reduction, the name has the form $L_j_k_X$, where j is the considered level, $k = K - 1$ is the number of acceptance marks considered by the formula, X is either **U** if the formula is unsatisfiable or **T** if the solver did not decide within the time limit. If X is **T**, a longer timeout may lead to further reductions. If the multi-level reduction is used, the automaton name contains the information from all levels. For example, the name ‘L1_5_U L2_3_U L3_1_T’ means that level 1 reduced the number of marks to 6 (reduction to 5 is impossible on this level), level 2 reduced it to 4, and level 3 to 2 as the QBF solver did not finish in the time limit when trying to reduce the number of marks to 1.

6 Experimental evaluation

To evaluate our reduction technique, we applied *telatko* to automata produced by the following process. We started with two sets of LTL formulas.

- One set contains all LTL formulas from *literature* that are provided by the tool *genltl* of the Spot library [9] 2.10.4. For parameterized formula patterns, we consider instances for all combinations of parameter values from 1 to 4.
- The second set consists of 400 random LTL formulas with 4 atomic propositions. These formulas were generated by the tool *randltl* of the Spot library.

On both these sets, we applied the tool *ltlfilt* of the Spot library to simplify the formulas and remove duplicates and formulas equivalent to *true* and *false*. After these steps, we had 348 LTL formulas from literature and 335 random formulas. Formulas from both sets have been translated to nondeterministic TELA by two state-of-the-art translators, namely *ltl2tgba* (used with option **-G** to get generic TELA) from the Spot library [9] and *ltl3tela* [15], and to deterministic TELA by *ltl3tela* with option **-D1** and by two

■ **Table 1** Considered translators and the numbers of *fails* and successfully constructed automata with *at most 1 mark* and with *at least 2 marks* for each translator and set of formulas.

translator	(version) ^{web}	348 formulas from literature			335 random formulas		
		fails	automata with		fails	automata with	
			at most 1 mark	at least 2 marks		at most 1 mark	at least 2 marks
1t12tgba -G	(2.10.4) ¹	0	278	70	0	320	15
1t13tela	(2.2.0) ²	18	239	91	0	286	49
1t13tela -D1	(2.2.0) ²	20	247	81	0	291	44
1t12dela	(21.0) ³	5	214	129	0	246	89
1t12dgra	(21.0) ³	12	102	234	0	130	205

state-of-the-art translators from the Owl library [14], namely `1t12dela` (known as Delag) [16] and `1t12dgra` (known as Rabinizer 4) [13]. Some translators failed on some formulas: they usually reached a timeout of 60 seconds or produced an automaton that cannot be parsed by the Spot library. Further, we have removed automata with 0 or 1 acceptance mark as there is a little point in reducing these. Table 1 shows the exact versions of the translators. For each translator and each set of formulas, the table also provides the number of fails, the number of produced automata with less than two marks, and the number of automata with at least two marks. The numbers of automata with at least two marks are typeset in bold as these automata are actually used for the experimental evaluation of our reduction technique.

To all automata, we have applied all single-level reductions and the multi-level reduction, always with incremental approach and without reducing the number of cubes. We do not reduce the number of cubes as our primary aim is to reduce the number of acceptance marks. The timeout for each QBF query was set to 30 seconds. All reductions have been performed by the tool `telatko` built with Spot library version 2.10.4 and Z3 version 4.8.15. The experiments have been run on a computer with Intel[®] Core[™] i7-8700 processor and 32 GB of memory running Ubuntu 20.04.4. We used the tool `autcross` of the Spot library to get the statistics of the reduced automata and the running times.

For each automata set identified by the translator and the set of formulas, Table 2 shows the cumulative numbers of marks in the input automata set and after each reduction, together with the reduction ratio and total time spent by the considered reduction. The column *solver timeout* shows the number of automata for which the last query to QBF solver did not finish within the 30 seconds limit. The timeout of the last QBF query means that the automaton may be potentially further reduced if a longer time limit is used. One can observe that a higher level sometimes achieves a smaller reduction than a lower level (e.g., compare level 1 and level 2 for `1t13tela` on automata coming from formulas from literature). This is caused by the QBF solver timeouts occurring earlier as formulas constructed by the higher level are more complex. The automata sets produced by `1t12dela` and `1t12dgra` on formulas from literature do not contain any automaton where level 2 or level 3 achieves a better result than level 1. However, all levels contribute to the reductions in the multi-level setting.

¹ <https://spot.lrde.epita.fr>

² <https://github.com/jurajmajor/1t13tela>

³ <https://owl.model.in.tum.de/>

■ **Table 2** For each automata set identified by the translator and the set of formulas, the table provides the cumulative number of acceptance marks before any reduction (in the box), after reduction of individual levels and after multi-level reduction (column *marks*). The column *reduction* shows the percentage of saved acceptance marks and *time* reports the cumulative reduction time in seconds. The column *solver timeout* indicates the number of instances where the last call to the QBF solver timed out.

translator	reduction level	reduction of marks in automata from formulas from literature				reduction of marks in automata from random formulas			
		marks	reduction [%]	time [s]	solver timeout	marks	reduction [%]	time [s]	solver timeout
ltl2tgba -G		198 marks in 70 automata				32 marks in 15 automata			
	1	198	0.0	48.5	0	32	0.0	8.4	0
	2	198	0.0	65.2	0	31	3.1	9.4	0
	3	189	4.5	409.8	7	26	18.8	43.9	1
	multi	189	4.5	427.6	7	26	18.8	44.9	1
ltl3tela		348 marks in 91 automata				120 marks in 49 automata			
	1	332	4.6	530.3	13	101	15.8	32.4	0
	2	334	4.0	551.0	14	100	16.7	32.3	0
	3	326	6.3	698.5	18	95	20.8	66.9	1
	multi	319	8.3	1619.2	18	95	20.8	73.4	1
ltl3tela -D1		272 marks in 81 automata				97 marks in 44 automata			
	1	272	0.0	383.1	9	95	2.1	23.8	0
	2	272	0.0	386.6	10	95	2.1	24.6	0
	3	272	0.0	950.2	14	92	5.2	54.1	0
	multi	272	0.0	1659.6	16	92	5.2	67.2	1
ltl2dela		523 marks in 129 automata				234 marks in 89 automata			
	1	386	26.2	811.4	18	154	34.2	89.0	0
	2	391	25.2	1071.6	19	153	34.6	123.6	0
	3	397	24.1	7326.8	26	149	36.3	172.7	2
	multi	378	27.7	9186.0	24	148	36.8	219.8	2
ltl2dgra		882 marks in 234 automata				491 marks in 205 automata			
	1	544	38.3	859.1	14	293	40.3	275.6	0
	2	554	37.2	1073.5	17	280	43.0	283.9	0
	3	553	37.3	1349.7	22	267	45.6	433.6	3
	multi	535	39.3	2434.0	23	264	46.2	411.7	2

23:16 Reducing Acceptance Marks in Emerson-Lei Automata by QBF Solving

■ **Table 3** The effect of multi-level reduction on all considered automata constructed from formulas from literature. A cell on coordinates (x, y) contains the number of automata that have been reduced from x to y acceptance marks. If the cell contains a sum of two numbers, the latter represents the number of automata where the attempt to reduce another mark has been unsuccessful due to a QBF solver timeout.

acceptance marks after the reduction	20-24											0+1
	15-19										0+4	0+1
	10-14								0+8	0+1		0
	9							0	0	0		0
	8							0+16	0+1	0	0	0
	7						0	0+2	0	0+1	0	0
	6					2+12	0+3	0	0+1	1	0	0
	5				10+5	2	0	0+1	1	0	0	0
	4		46+10	14	5+2	10	2+1	4	4	0+1		0
	3	73+2	5+2	2	0	1	0	0	0+1	0	0	
	2	96+10	27	8+1	4	2	0	0+1	0	0	0	
1	149	11	4	2	1	1	0	0	0	0		
0	27	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10-14	15-19	20-24
		acceptance marks before the reduction										

■ **Table 4** The effect of multi-level reduction on all considered automata constructed from random formulas. The meaning of each cell is the same as in Table 3.

acceptance marks after the reduction	5				0	0+1	0	0	0	
	4			0	2	0+1	0	0	1	
	3		11+1	8	2	0	0	1	0	
	2	107+3	29+1	22	1	1	0	0	0	
	1	188	10	9	0	0	0	0	0	
	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	
		acceptance marks before the reduction								

Table 3 shows the effect of multi-level reduction to the number of acceptance marks in individual automata constructed from formulas from literature. The table indicates that in many cases only 1 or 2 marks can be saved. However, the achieved reduction is substantial for some automata with a higher number of original acceptance marks. For example, in 26 cases, we have reduced 7 or more acceptance marks to only 4 or less. Table 4 shows the same information for automata constructed from random formulas.

Figure 4 presents the time spent by multi-level reduction on individual automata of each automata set. The charts show a pleasing finding that for every set, most automata are reduced in under 5 seconds and the high cumulative running times are caused by a relatively small number of complicated automata.

■ **Figure 4** Running times of `telatko` on individual automata of each automata set. Automata sets constructed from formulas from literature are in the upper graph, automata sets constructed from random formulas are in the lower graph. Each line shows the time (y axis) needed by `telatko` to process the x^{th} automaton of the set, where automata in the set are ordered by their processing time.

7 Conclusions

We have presented a method reducing the number of acceptance marks in transition-based Emerson-Lei automata with use of QBF solving and without altering automata structure. We have implemented the method in a tool called `telatko`. The current applications of the tool are twofold. First, it can reduce the number of acceptance marks of a given TELA. Second, it discloses how tools producing TELA are economical with acceptance marks. The presented experimental results show that the tool can indeed reduce the number of acceptance marks in automata produced by all considered state-of-the-art LTL to automata translators. Further, it clearly shows that the translators of the Owl library are significantly less economical with acceptance marks than the other two translators.

The reduction of acceptance marks is not the only application of the presented approach. For example, it can be easily adapted to look for an equivalent automaton with the same structure and an acceptance formula of a specific form (e.g., without any $\text{Fin } m$ atoms). Even though the QBF queries can be time-consuming, in practice one can often find a good trade-off between speed and efficiency by adjusting the formula precision and choosing a reasonable timeout.

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23:20 Reducing Acceptance Marks in Emerson-Lei Automata by QBF Solving

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